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InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D1.4. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN FIRST UPDATE

FiBL

Universidade de Vigo

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Summary

This Data Management Plan (DMP) has been updated after 36 months of implementation of InBestSoil to efficiently contribute to the management of research data collected or generated in the course of InBestSoil work. This DMP explains how these data are going to be stored, published, cited and made FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) beyond the project life. Our goal is to meet the requirements of excellent scientific practice and to allow for accessibility, interoperability, and reproducibility of InBestSoil research results. This DMP also aims to contribute to the development of the European Soil Observatory (EUSO). To ensure that relevant knowledge and project outputs (including data) are fed to the EUSO, datasets of relevance to the EUSO have been identified.

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	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	x
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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1. Executive Summary

Purpose

This Data Management Plan (DMP) has been updated after 36 months of implementation of InBestSoil to efficiently contribute to the management of research data collected or generated in the course of InBestSoil work. This DMP explains how these data are being stored, published, cited and made FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) beyond the project life. Our goal is to meet the requirements of excellent scientific practice and to allow for accessibility, interoperability, and reproducibility of InBestSoil research results. This DMP also aims to contribute to the development of the European Soil Observatory (EUSO). To ensure that relevant knowledge and project outputs (including data) are fed to the EUSO, datasets of relevance to the EUSO have been identified.

Intended audience

i) researchers involved in soil health, soil management, business models based on soil, valuation of ecosystem services provided by soil, incentives and policies related to soil, ii) EC officers responsible for the EU Soil Observatory; iii) agronomists, foresters, land managers and land planners modelling soil processes, fertility, carbon dynamics, contaminants, biodiversity, economic valuation of ecosystem services, business models; iv) public authorities and policymakers working on soil monitoring schemes, policy design and compliance on soil health and monitoring, and support on land-use decisions, zoning, rural development, or ecosystem restoration; v) agri-environmental consultants and extension services for operational advice and development of best management practices to improve soil health and develop economic investments to increase soil health and promote rural growth; and vi) EU and global datasets and networks (e.g. Soil BON, GSP-FAO, WoSIS) for harmonization and interoperability.

Description of the main activities

Review of the first version of InBestSoil Data Management Plan by WP coordinators and task leaders to assess if the data being generated in the implementation of the project was aligned with this version. For this, we checked the format of data generated in each task, and included the datasets already made accessible. In addition, we followed the indications provided by the Mission Soil Cluster on Data & Knowledge Management to update this deliverable, providing new extensions for data files to make our data more re-usable, such as .csv or .json.

Key results

- **Result 1:** Data generated by InBestSoil is uploaded to the InBestSoil Community in Zenodo with file formats that allow the re-use of the data, by using with standardized international units, providing DOI, standardized keywords and metadata, CC-BY or CC-BY-SA license, and funder information.

Research and practice implications

This deliverable provides the guidelines followed to ensure that all data generated by our project is properly stored in public repositories with the use of appropriate identification, formats, units, keywords, metadata, licenses and funder/grant information, so it can be efficiently found, accessed and re-used by any user outside the project, and beyond the project lifetime. In this deliverable, we show in detail how our strategy on data management is being conducted for this purpose, using the InBestSoil Community in Zenodo as main repository, together with the sequence read archive (SRA) of the NCBI database for DNA sequencing data for soil microbial communities.

Policy implications

This deliverable ensures that all data generated by the project is accessible to policy-makers and public authorities working on soil monitoring schemes, policy design and soil health in general. To such an end, we indicate the formats in which data is stored (the vast majority of the datasets will be made available as .xlsx, .csv and .json formats, and to a lesser extent as .txt, .enl, .pdf, .do, .dta, .bam or .fastq).

Conclusion

This update of InBestSoil Management Plan defines how data is being stored during the project to ensure its long-term availability making them findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, by following internationally agreed metadata, keywords, formats, units and license. In such a way, we aligned with the indications provided by the Mission Soil Cluster on Data & Knowledge Management.

2. Data summary

Data collection is an essential part of the InBestSoil project which aims to co-create a framework to promote investment in soil health, by developing an economic valuation system of the ecosystem services delivered by a healthy soil and the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentive development. This assessment relies on seven lighthouses and two living labs.

Firstly, the data gathered derive from the collection of existing databases, outcomes from previous and ongoing European and national projects and literature reviews (sources: Zenodo, PubMed, SCOPUS, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, etc.). We re-used this data in order to i) select benefit transfer methodology for the estimation of non-market values by using a meta-analysis approach (WP3); ii) identify current business models linked to soil health enhancement and select the most appropriate tools for the analyses of potential business models (WP4); and iii) horizontal mapping review of existing European, national and regional policy incentives and nudges contributing to preserving and restoring soil health (WP6). These data is being re-stored in the following formats: Excel files (.xlsx), Comma-Separated Values files (.csv), JavaScript Object Notation files (.json), text files (.txt) or EndNote Clarivates files (.enl).

Secondly, there is data corresponding to lighthouses and living labs, such as classification of soil, climate, property, crop history, land management and experimental design of the living lab sites (geolocation, plot characteristics, replications, treatment applied, management practices, sampling and analyses) (WP3). These data is being stored into Excel files (.xlsx), Comma-Separated Values file (.csv) and JavaScript Object Notation files (.json).

Thirdly, we also collected data related to stakeholders' information and contacts, gathered in Excel datasets (.xlsx). Given the personal nature of some of these data, it will never become public nor accessible outside the project, being used only by project partners for work purposes, and the Excel file will be deleted at the end of the project. Therefore, it will be only shared internally on Teams.

Fourthly, we created new data from the analyses of the soil samples collected in all lighthouses and living labs in WP3. Selected indicators for key ecosystem services (provision of food, fibre, raw materials or water, climate regulation, water/air purification, soil pollution reduction, nutrient cycling, biodiversity, habitat for organisms, flood regulation and water storage, cultural heritage, cultural identity, recreation, aesthetics, etc) were measured in each lighthouse and living lab. These data are being stored in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx) and made public as .xlsx files, Comma-Separated Values files (.csv) and JavaScript Object Notation files (.json). WP3 has also produced new DNA sequencing data of soil biological communities (taxonomic), which will be stored in .bam and .fastq files, that can be operated with the open access R software. Sequencing data will be stored in the sequence read archive (SRA) of the NCBI database. Finally, data generated from Life Cycle Assessment and the economic valuation was stored in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx) and will be made public as Comma-Separated Values file (.csv) and JavaScript Object Notation files (.json) (WP3).

Fifthly, for the analysis of current business models (WP4), the SOLm food system model implemented provided output data as .xlsx, .csv and .json formats. The SOLm model is implemented in R. The farm survey raw data was stored as Excel files (.xlsx), Comma-Separated Values file (.csv) and JavaScript Object Notation files (.json). For data analysis, STATA is being used, where scripts will be stored as do-files (.do), and processed farm survey data will be stored with the .dta extension.

Finally, for the assessment of new business models for soil health (WP5), the data gathered from (semi-structured) interviews, stakeholders' meetings and focus groups is being stored in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx), .pdf and .docx files, and will be made public as Excel files (.xlsx), Comma-Separated Values file (.csv), JavaScript Object Notation files (.json) and text files (.txt). The quantitative research activities in WP5 will be managed with R or STATA software, and the output data will be stored as do-files (.do), dta-files (.dta), Comma-Separated Values file (.csv), and JavaScript Object Notation files (.json). In all cases, maps or network data is being elaborated to show results, and will be stored as .png or .jpeg.

In addition, Carbon farming certification scheme will be analysed (WP6) with the aim to evaluate the possibility to complement it with indicators that ensure the accountability of soil health results beyond carbon, introducing the supplementary indicators provided by WP3. Financial and economic incentives have been analysed as a part of value proposition (WP6). These data will be stored as Excel files (.xlsx), Comma-Separated Values file (.csv), JavaScript Object Notation files (.json), text files (.txt) and pdf files.

Overall, the datasets generated by InBestSoil to fulfil its objectives are diverse but mostly numeric and, to a lesser extent, text as a result of some of the surveys/questionnaires, and images for mapping and network planning. Datasets mainly consist of observational data (geolocation data, experimental design data, surveys/questionnaires, economic and financial assessment, business models assessment), experimental data captured by field and laboratory equipment (soil properties delivery of ecosystem services) and simulation data (models applied to assess business models performance in WP4).

Regarding the size of the generated data, many datasets are being produced, but none is overly big, which allows its collection on spreadsheets and text files for easy accessibility.

Data from soil analyses in the different lighthouses and living labs (WP3) is of great interest to feed **EUSO** with indicators representing physical, chemical and biological characteristics and processes of soils from different land uses and regions. We believe the data generated by InBestSoil will be useful for researchers in the field of soil health and quality, land managers, public administration and professionals/business sectors in the field of soil management and soil recovery.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Due to the fact that the collected datasets are diverse and belong to different fields, the metadata standard used to describe them follows the Dublin Core Schema, a flexible and commonly used standard, also adopted by the European OpenAIRE repository. All data is being stored in the InBestSoil Community within Zenodo, making it publicly available and easily findable using proper metadata. Each time a dataset is uploaded, the metadata is introduced manually, including the keywords to increase its findability and potential use. Preferably, the chosen keywords are those suggested by Zenodo (GEMET and MeSH), and when more specific keywords are needed, project experts from the WPs who are familiar with the most commonly used keywords in their field write them. All datasets include some pages or associated files with description of authors, institutions, data factors and variable names and units.

3.2. Making data accessible

All datasets supporting publications are being made openly and publicly available on the OpenAire repository of Zenodo upon acceptance of the manuscript for publication. Up to date, the following datasets have been already uploaded to Zenodo, freely accessible:

- Soil data included in article "Bogunovic et al. 2025. The Role of Grassland Land Use in Enhancing Soil Resilience and Climate Adaptation in Periurban Landscapes. *Agronomy* 15, 1589", as .xlxs, .csv and .json files.
- Soil data included in article "Brezinscak and Bogunovic 2025. Optimizing Tillage and Straw Management for Improved Soil Physical Properties and Yield. *Land* 2025, 14, 376", as .xlxs, .csv and .json files.
- Soil data included in article "Galic et al. 2025. Soil C-CO₂ Emissions Across Different Land Uses in a Peri-Urban Area of Central Croatia. *Land* 2025, 14, 1876", as .xlxs, .csv and .json files.
- Soil health on Swiss arable farms: data covering soil management practices, farm characteristics and decision drivers, as .xlxs, .csv and .json files for data, and .pdf file for description.
- Soil data included in article "Pereira et al. 2024. A simple method to assess flood regulation supply in urban lawns" as .xlxs, .csv and .json files.
- Data included in article "Pereira et al 2024. A simple method to map pollination ecosystem services potential in urban lawns", as .xlxs, .csv and .json files for vegetation data, and .cbf, .prj, .sbn, .sbx and .shp files for GIS data to open them with GIS software.

All datasets generated along the project work plan and not published before the 31 December 2026 (end of project) will be made public three years after this date (31 December 2029), regardless of manuscript publication. The repository Zenodo assigns a DOI for persistent identification and citability of the dataset. Only data gathered by partners outside the project work plan and protected by IPR, or inside the work plan but containing confidential information (e.g. related to personal interviews, stakeholder's contact information), are kept closed for privacy reasons.

Data is also shared among members of work packages continuously as it is generated throughout the InBestSoil Teams library associated to the O365 platform of tools for collaborative work (online platform belonging to beneficiary UPCT). Furthermore, when a dataset turns openly accessible, it will be announced on the web page of the InBestSoil project www.inbestsoil.eu, where a link to the dataset on Zenodo will be available.

The vast majority of the datasets are available as .xlsx, .csv and .json formats, and to a lesser extent as .txt, .enl, .pdf, .do, .dta, .cbf, .prj, .sbn, .sbx and .shp, .bam or .fastq (Table 1). Information about the software needed to open these common files is provided within each dataset or file.

Table 1. Summary of data generated during InBestSoil project life. The WP in which they are generated, and the format of each one are also indicated.

Data	WP	Format
Project stakeholders' information and contacts datasets	WP2	.xlsx, .csv, .json
Literature review, databases and outcomes of projects	WP3, WP4, WP6	.xlsx, .csv, .json .txt, .pdf, .enl
History of lighthouses and living labs	WP3	.xlsx, .csv, .json
Soil health indicators and GIS data	WP3	.xlsx, .csv, .json, .cbf, .prj, .sbn, .sbx and .shp
Soil DNA sequencing data	WP3	.bam, .fastq, .xlsx, .csv, .json
Life Cycle Assessment	WP3	.xlsx, .csv, .json
Economic valuation	WP3	.xlsx, .csv, .json
Farm surveys	WP4	.xlsx, .csv, .json, .do, .dta, .pdf
Analysis of current business models (implementation of SOLm model)	WP4	.xlsx, .csv, .json, .pdf
New business models by interviews, meetings and focus groups	WP5	.xlsx, .csv, .json, .pdf, .txt, .do, .dta
Maps of new business models	WP5	.png, .jpeg
Indicators to be integrated in Carbon Farming Certification methodologies	WP6	.xlsx, .csv, .json
Financial and economic incentives	WP6	.pdf, .txt

3.3. Making data interoperable

The depositors strive to use commonly and internationally used metadata in their field of research, using those available on GEMET, MeSH, EuroSciVoc, Agrovoc or GloSIS. Data variable names are checked for international consensus on Agrovoc or GloSIS. The data units used are those commonly accepted by the international scientific community, and the International System of Units.

4. Increase data re-use

In general, the data generated by the project use the Creative Commons license framework, while the particular type of license for each dataset is decided individually, though the recommendation will be either CC-BY or CC-BY-SA.

The data will remain re-usable after the end of the project by anyone interested in it, with no access or time restrictions, according to the possibilities provided by the Zenodo repository. Each archived dataset has its own permanent repository ID (DOI) and is easily accessible. Most data are available without restrictions, which are reserved for datasets subjected to IPR and confidentiality. In these cases, it would be possible to sign agreements to access and use the data by external users, which have to be approved by the consortium or the institution holding the IP rights.

Since all datasets will support publication in peer-reviewed open access journals, they achieve the scientific standards of quality, such as the validation of the sample, replicability and comparability with similar studies).

In addition to the announcement of new data uploads in the InBestSoil website, the social media profiles created by the project disseminate this information with links to the webpage and the datasets on Zenodo. Internally, all partners and EUSO are being informed by email about the availability of new datasets, including the link to Zenodo.

5. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, InBestSoil beneficiaries also manage other research outputs generated within the workplan of the project, which will be openly accessible, findable and usable (Table 2).

Table 2. Key exploitable results from InBestSoil, with the exploitation strategy to be followed and the protection mechanism.

Partner	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Related WP	Exploitation strategy / Exploitation path	Protection mechanism
UPCT	Toolkit of soil health indicators and total economic value of soil health	WP3	Open licence for end-users to apply the knowledge to assess soil health indicators to further give them a monetary value	CC-BY licence
UPCT	Web-based calculator for the economic value of soil ecosystem services	WP3	Utility model for end-users to apply the process to give a monetary value to their soils	Utility model
CMCC	Policy conditions and catalogues of existing soil health economic and policy incentives	WP6	Webinar hosted by the Soil Community Platform; Academic Conferences; events by other relevant projects (e.g. NATURANCE festival); Science-policy events in conjunction with BLOserviceES project (e.g. EU and/or)	Report and open access scientific publication
CMCC	Toolbox of incentive schemes for soil health	WP6	Distributed via repositories (e.g. Zenodo)	Open access database
CMCC	Report on Policy recommendations for soil health protection.	WP6	Distributed standalone and as a part of European assessment reports such as by EFDRR , EEA .	Report and open access scientific publication

6. Allocation of resources

There are no costs associated with the described mechanisms to make the database FAIR and long term preserved since we are using the Zenodo repository. Data files quality is checked by the data manager who is also responsible for submitting them to Zenodo. The project coordinator has the ultimate responsibility for data management in the project.

7. Data security

On one hand, the Zenodo repository takes care of security and backup of the deposited data. On the other hand, regarding the data-sharing process involved between partners during research, we are using the Teams Online libraries associated to the O365 platform within the institutional account of UPCT, which include the data protection services provided by Microsoft to prevent the loss of data.

8. Ethics

The ethical aspects related to the personal data collected in InBestSoil datasets are addressed in project deliverable D1.1. Ethics principles and guidelines for protection of personal data.

